

**UNCOVERING THE SPECTRUM: EXPLORING CHALLENGES FACED
BY TRANSGENDER PEOPLE WITHIN AND BEYOND
THE LGBTQIA+ COMMUNITY**

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Uncovering the Spectrum: Exploring Challenges Faced by Transgender People within and beyond the LGBTQIA+ Community

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Abstract

The study delved into the multifaceted challenges encountered by transgender individuals within and beyond the LGBTQ+ community. It sought to comprehend their lived experiences, encompassing discrimination, social dynamics, familial rejection, mental health implications, and hurdles in personal relationships. Employing a phenomenological research design. The seven transgender participants were given the option of virtual or face-to-face interviews, conducted in a confidential and secure environment in the Mandaluyong area. A semi-structured interviewing technique was employed, with interview questions validated by experts in Psychology. Thematic analysis was utilized to identify emergent themes, with a sample size of seven achieving data saturation. The study identified three superordinate themes: (1) Inclusivity and Setbacks in the LGBTQIA+ Community, (2) Experienced Challenges and Barriers and (3) Impact of Support Systems in Overcoming Hurdles. The findings revealed a complex landscape for transgender individuals, with both inclusivity and setbacks within the LGBTQIA+ community. Discrimination, social dynamics, and challenges in personal relationships emerged as prominent themes. The LGBTQIA+ community offers belongingness, progression, and growth, there are inherent difficulties in fitting into societal norms within the community. Future research is recommended to explore interventions and practices fostering more supportive and inclusive environment for LGBTQIA+ individuals, acknowledging the existing challenges and promoting growth and empowerment.

Keywords: *transgender challenges, societal biases and legal obstacles, Filipino Transgender Rights*

Introduction

Transgender people experiences have been affected by ongoing inequity and antagonism, repeating a long history of societal prejudice. Trans people's human rights are particularly vulnerable when their name and gender details on legal documents do not match their gender identity or expression. A transgender person's gender identity differs from the sex assigned at birth. Their journey toward self-actualization and effectiveness often encounters significant obstacles, such as social prejudice, legal barriers, and personal pain. Transgender people's experiences have shed light on the complicated web of obstacles they encounter daily as they have become more visible and vocal. At the foundation of acts of assault and prejudice is the purpose of disciplining based on predetermined beliefs as to what one's sexual orientation ought to be, with an unambiguous understanding of what a gender orientation is. This arrangement produces a legal vacuum as well as an environment that perpetuates prejudice and discrimination against them. The health of transgender adults is disproportionately affected by discrimination, stigma, and violence, which increases the risk of HIV/AIDS, chronic disease, substance abuse, mental illness, and violence. They also experience difficulties in accessing health care and insurance. These inequities have gotten worse, especially for transgender people of color, because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Transgender people often undergo medical procedures such as hormone therapy and surgery. Transgender patients claim that the biggest barrier to healthcare is a shortage of medical practitioners who are more knowledgeable about transgender medicine, even though guidelines and data support an existing paradigm for treating transgender people. Treatment of transgender patients is not covered in conventional medical curricula, and too few doctors understand this and are willing to provide treatment.

Transgender people also suffer workplace discrimination and privacy violations. A lot of them have lost their jobs due to bias. Refusal to hire, and even physical and sexual violence. Transgenders often earn less than their cisgender co-workers, they also might have limited access to employee benefits, such as leaves and retirement plans. Due to extreme unemployment and poverty, one in eight people turn to the underground economy of prostitution and drug trafficking to make a living. Transgender people also have limited access to public places, they are often discriminated against utilizing public facilities like restrooms. While in custody, transgender prisoners often face harassment and abuse. Most of them are at odds with their gender identity, which leads to a higher risk of violence and mental health problems. This violates their civil rights to equal treatment and safety. Different countries have different legal protections for transgender people, leading to inconsistent implementation of human rights. Transgender people suffer a lot of discrimination in employment, education, etc., and in some jurisdictions, they are discriminated against due to a lack of adequate legal protections. Discrimination and violence are common issues among the LGBTQ+ community; these issues must be addressed because they impact not only the health but also the well-being of this community. These issues require intermediate attention to avoid more dangerous situations that can be resolved before the problem escalates. According to Hazir (2019) The negative repercussions of LGBTQ discrimination include an increased tendency for LGBTQ people to commit suicide and have poor physical health because of excessive stress. Even more than that, according to JL (2021), the likelihood of experiencing violence in one's life is still four times

higher for LGBT individuals than for homosexuals. According to FBI statistics from 2019, there have been more anti-LGBTQIA+ hate crimes and more instances of police brutality. With knowledge of this life-threatening condition, we need to not only be informed, but we need to act and shed light on what is happening within this community. In addition to discrimination and violence, the rights, safety, and health of LGBTQ+ people are also affected. These create new problems for communities because they sidestep the equality and fairness that communities deserve. According to Sanchez et al. (2020), LGBTQ+ people view health care as a second priority, exacerbating the stigma they face. As these disadvantages arise, the treatment and health care of the LGBTQ+ community have been hard to deal with. The unfair treatment uplifts the lack of spaces for safety, rights, and protection for the community as they were considered “different.” By focusing on these issues, society will become more open and empower LGBTQ+ people to be free from discrimination and violence. These will also encourage the law to provide equality and fairness about their rights, safety, and health, which need adequate attention for the LGBTQ+ community.

Due to certain people's refusal to acknowledge their gender, some members of the lesbian and gay community encounter prejudice all around the world. Many transgender people suffer assaults, receive negative feedback from others, are occasionally rejected by family members, and are denied the opportunity to run for any community-related office due to their gender. Every transgender person working for the government faces criticism, which serves as one of the triggers for resentment and rejection of their gender in our community. Most transgendered teens are aware of using smoke, alcohol, or drugs to forget all their issues or to be dispersed on the street, but some transgender teens do face abuse and cruel comments from their parents, which causes them to rebel. Some of them share their opinions and emotions on social media to protect themselves from bullying and prejudice, while others are reluctant to speak out for fear that their friends will reject or ostracize them because of their gender. Most transgender people are also freer to express themselves on social media, which is another factor. According to Mayo Clinic (2023), Gender minority stress is linked to transgender and gender-diverse people seeking preventive health care and health screenings less often than other people. This may be due to a lack of insurance, being denied care, difficulty finding a health care provider with expertise in transgender care, or fear of discrimination in the health care setting. Due to gender minority stress, transgender people may be at higher risk for emotional and psychological abuse, physical and sexual violence, sexually transmitted infections, substance abuse, and mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts.

Trans people face many difficulties, both within and outside the LGBTQ+ community. LGBTQ people lack acceptance within the larger LGBTQ community, and trans people can also experience prejudice, rejection, and marginalization. It can also be caused by misunderstandings, biases, or a lack of understanding of trans identities and experiences. Some trans people suffer from transphobia, which is a term used to describe hostility, anxiety, or prejudice against transgender people. Invisibility is one of the challenges that transgender people frequently struggle with. They strive to gain visibility and acceptance within the LGBTQ+ community. Some may feel that the hobbies and experiences of cisgender (non-transgender) people are ignored or glossed over. Beyond the LGBTQ community, transgender people experience discrimination, which they often stumble upon in a range of settings, including the workplace, classrooms, homes, health care, and public spaces. They may have difficulty accessing basic services and experience harassment, denial of rights, or unfair treatment. Violence and hate crimes are some of the challenges they face within their communities. The prevalence of violence and hate crimes against trans people is alarming. Because of their gender identity, they often face heightened threats of physical assault, verbal abuse, harassment, and even murder. Additionally, there are legal barriers, as transgender people do not always have access to adequate legal protections. They may encounter difficulties updating their gender marker on identification documents, obtaining correct medical care, or gaining legal recognition of their gender identity. Transgender people struggle with health care inequities, and trans people's access to professional, inclusive health care is often hindered. They might experience prejudice from healthcare professionals, limited access to gender-affirming therapies, and difficulties getting support for their mental health. Lastly, the isolation and social stigma, transgender people may experience social stigma, which may harm their overall well-being and cause them to become isolated. It can also be challenging for them to build strong social networks and maintain connections with friends, family, and peers. It's necessary to understand that the difficulties confronted by using transgender humans would possibly alternate based on a variety of conditions, as well as their geographic region, cultural background, and private circumstances. Addressing these issues and building a more inclusive and authentic society requires a concerted effort to raise awareness, educate the public, and protect the rights of transgender people.

This study delves into the unique experiences and obstacles faced by transgender people. Here in the Philippines, being engaged in LGBTQ+ is a big controversy for each Filipino, whether it may be transphobic, homophobic, or prejudiced toward the LGBTQ+ community. Researchers have studied this topic, which is not only compelling but also relevant and necessary today. People should be aware that within the LGBTQ+ community, trans people often face their own set of challenges, such as acceptance, inclusion, and belonging. It also reflects the complexities of the LGBTQ+ community and trans people. The intersection of identities, and sometimes even classes, results in unique dynamics worth exploring, yet unknown to Filipinos who do not belong to the LGBTQ+ community.

With the rapid pace of the world today, it is prevalent that society accepts individuals who identify as transgender, although it cannot be avoided that these individuals may find some problems when it comes to society accepting them. If the problem is not addressed, trans people may continue to face discrimination. According to Beyond Blue Organization (2022), Despite growing social acceptance of LGBTQ+ individuals and increased visibility in the media and public life, many LGBTQ+ individuals still face discrimination, harassment, and assault at work, school, and social settings. Overt acts of bias and discrimination (such as denying jobs or promotions

to people who openly identify as transgender), as well as more subtle but equally damaging forms of discrimination that perpetuate negative preconceptions and feelings of difference (e.g., using the word 'gay' and 'faggot' as a derogatory term). The continued development of this problem may lead to some worrying issues such as health and safety. A study done by James, S. et al. (2016). The Report of the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey. Washington, DC: National Center for Transgender Equality. Transgender people, especially Black trans women, experience varying degrees of physical violence. This is particularly true for transgender people who are participating in sex work and other informal or criminalized economies. Brutal murders of transgender women occur at such an alarming rate, often with little response from law enforcement, that the American Medical Association declared violence against transgender people an epidemic in 2019.

Research Questions

The aim of this study was to find out the challenges encountered by transgender individuals within and beyond the LGBTQ+ community. In this study, the following questions were addressed:

1. How do transgender people deal with their identities and relationships in a society that typically excludes non-binary and gender-diverse people?
2. How does LGBTQ+ discrimination affect transgender people, and what causes it?
3. What kind of strategies can colleagues and advocacy groups use to support transgender people both within and outside the LGBTQIA+ community and foster acceptance and understanding?

Literature Review

This study is designed to provide a comprehensive examination faced by transgender individuals. The researcher should be able to identify relationships between studies, understand contradictions, and lastly identify research gaps. The ambition of the LGBTQ+ community is to unify, diversity, and establish inclusivity, in the case of transgenders, this seeks for them to ensure that these individuals are not only recognized by actively embraced within the LGBTQ+ community. This is a vital step towards a more equitable and supportive environment for its members of the community.

Every individual is inherently free and possesses an equal level of worth and entitlements. They are endowed with a conscience and the capacity for critical thinking, obligating them to interact with one another in a spirit of unity and mutual support. The recognition and fulfillment of this right is imperative for all members of our society. However, regrettably, the prevailing reality contradicts this fundamental right, as a significant portion of the population continues to endure discrimination, thereby depriving them of its benefits. In a study conducted by Ramos (2019), it was found that the discrimination faced by individuals who identify as LGBTQIA not only results in instances of bullying but can escalate to the horrifying extent of physical attacks. These acts of abuse inflict immediate harm and have far-reaching consequences, such as heightened levels of depression and anxiety among the victims. The detrimental impact of such mental distress can even extend to suicidal thoughts and other grave outcomes, emphasizing the urgency of addressing the discrimination faced by LGBTQIA individuals. Gender discrimination has a significant impact on individuals' lives, causing distress when they are denied opportunities based on their gender. It is unjust to deny people their rights because of their gender, as gender should not be a determining factor. Even transgender individuals, who face discrimination and societal rejection solely because of their gender identity, are not exempt from this injustice. They endure constant harassment and disparities due to a lack of understanding among the public. It is crucial to recognize that transgender individuals are an important part of our society and should be given equal rights and acceptance Mozumder (2022). There are numerous instances of discrimination against the different parts of the LGBTQ community. They are frustrated with wanting to live a normal life, but what the people around them give and show is cruelty towards them. They are currently experiencing a difficult time due to the continued lack of acceptance from society. It is necessary for us to be more open to these kinds of matters. This has been going on for a long time, yet we continue to turn a blind eye to this system. They face countless problems, which is why the minds of the citizens and society should be opened to them.

These studies failed to recognize that it is a must to uphold individual freedom and foster equal rights. Nonetheless, it is also important to remember that society embraces a broad range of opinions and views. Many people don't adhere to the belief that every person naturally has an equal amount of importance and privileges, and this does not always indicate the presence of prejudice. According to Turban (2022), It raises a perspective among particular people that argues the significant impact of societal norms and values on the development and manifestation of human relationships and behavior. There is a claim that the protection of individuals' rights to express their thoughts freely and hold their own opinions should be preserved, particularly in cases where their points of view might differ from prevailing standards in society. According to Pearce (2020), Advocating LGBTQ rights and promoting awareness is important. Furthermore, it is crucial to acknowledge that the process of altering deeply ingrained views and attitudes requires a considerable amount of time and constructive discussion.

Meanwhile, a considerable amount of research has been done on how transgender people suffer from discrimination and violence and its impacts. According to Kcomt (2019), there is more discrimination against transgender people than gay, lesbian, and bisexual individuals, which affects their health and well-being. With that, it doomed the vulnerability of transgender people and increased the microaggression towards them. An identity non-affirmation microaggression is also part of this, wherein it is common to misuse the preferred pronouns, be stared at in public places, be misunderstood toward its transition phase, or be commanded to use a public facility

based on gender (Par & Howe, 2019). However, less attention has been paid to how transgender people overcome and outgrow these sufferings despite how crucial and challenging the experiences the LGBTQ+ community has been through.

Despite the importance of the studies about the challenges that transgender people have encountered outside the LGBTQIA+ community, few researchers have studied lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer (LGBTQIA+) people are more likely to experience sexual violence than their heterosexual, cisgender counterparts. These discrepancies, which can be seen in the various definitions of rape and sexual assault, have inspired us researchers to further investigate the causes, consequences, and societal reactions to sexual violence among LGBTQIA+ populations. Research tended to focus on discrimination against heterosexual people sexually abusing the LGBTQIA+ community but forgot that there are also abuses and discrimination among them. Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is associated with negative life outcomes such as physical and mental health problems, financial stress, job insecurity, and fear of/actualized loss of custody of children because of abuse (Todd et al., 2019). On the other hand, relatively less study has been done on IPV in queer relationships, even though there are many studies focusing on IPV in opposite-gender couples. In addition, many studies on IPV, whether they involved heterosexual or LGBTQ subjects, were quantitative (e.g., Kimmes et al., 2019; Spencer et al., 2020). Across-the-board prejudice, a lack of visibility, social support, and compassion may combine to make it more difficult for LGBTQ+ IPV survivors to flee risky settings and heal from the trauma they underwent. Since many queer and trans women have had relationships with men at some time in their lives, statistics on queer women and IPV are not always restricted to female perpetrators, which is a challenge with the current incidence rates of IPV among LGBTQ+ women. Students who were members of the LGBTQ community at this time had difficulty expressing themselves in public, not just at school but also at home. What are the difficulties and struggles they experience in public and at home? LGBTQ students, for instance, are not upfront about their emotions since they are afraid of being judged by everyone, especially their relatives. Some community members are not accepting because of who they are. According to Kosciw et al. (2020), most LGBTQ students have heard homophobic remarks, and some LGBTQ students have heard negative comments about gender expression in schools within the past year. In addition, transgender and gender-diverse students are exposed to more negative school experiences compared to their cisgender heterosexual and cisgender sexual minority counterparts. In a study of many transgender youth, Day et al. (2018) found that Transgender youth were more likely to experience victimization and bullying and to report a negative school climate. LGBTQ students who have other marginalized identities (e.g., ethnic and racial Minorities (non-Christian, low-income, and economically marginalized [LIEM]) may experience increased incidents of discrimination and oppression in schools. In a recent study of many of black LGBTQ students, Truong et.al. (2020) found that some of the participants experienced harassment or assault as a result of their sexual orientation, gender identity, and race, with gender-diverse black students experiencing greater levels of victimization than their Unfortunately, research about the experiences of LGBTQ students who share other marginalized identities is scant, and the available results are mixed and do not provide a clear picture of their experiences (see review in Abreu & Kenny, 2018).

In the previous research conducted by Hanson et al. (2019), there were respondents who responded "not sure" to the question about sexual orientation and may have felt uncertain about how to define their sexuality. They are not sure about their identity, and they are outside the LGBT, but they have confusion about themselves or they hide their identity. Despite this early research about understanding the experiences of LGBTQ it has remained unclear to the individuals beyond the LGBT group so why are many people scared about their identity or what is the reason for their confusion about their identity. The confusion or worry surrounding one's identification can be complicated and multifaceted. One of the causes is societal expectations due to the fact society often imposes rigid norms and expectations involving gender, sexuality, and identity. These expectations can be deeply ingrained and may not align with an individual's inner feeling of self. When anyone feels that their identity deviates from societal norms, it can create confusion and concern due to the plausible for judgment, discrimination, or rejection. The previous research of Swiatek, Ryan, & Peralta-Catipon (2021) about Older Adults in an LGBT Residential Community to understand how a supportive and safe environment for LGBT members, especially transgender people's occupational participation and well-being but this research is exclusive to the individual who lives in residential and the question remains what is the different perspective of LGBT individuals who live in rural or politically conservative locations about their safe space in their occupation. What are their experiences inside and outside of their community? Transgender folks in rural environments may additionally face special challenges with limited access to assets because transgender individuals in rural areas might also have constrained access to specialized healthcare providers, help groups, or transgender-friendly services or lack of appreciation and acceptance. Traditional values and conservative attitudes typical in some rural communities can lead to a lack of perception and acceptance of transgender individuals.

In addition to what has already been discussed regarding the various difficulties faced by transgenders and the LGBTQ+ community, it remains clear that there are still problems and difficulties that are not recognized or addressed within the community. Discrimination is still pervasive in society, and as society advances, more and more issues and difficulties continue to arise. According to Shah et al. (2018) Stigma, social exclusion, and eventual exclusion from society make transgender people's lives even more difficult. These challenges have influenced their daily behavior, making them exposed to risky behavior. Furthermore, protection and legislation pertaining to LGBTQ+ health care are not given sufficient attention. Stigma, discrimination, and a lack of information continue to be prevalent difficulties for LGBTQ individuals while obtaining health care services. Inadequate rural services and support amplify these concerns, negatively hurting physical and mental health and adding to the disadvantage (Henriquez & Ahmad, 2021).

Transgender individuals face a multitude of challenges, spanning both within and beyond the LGBTQ+ community. Key concerns like

discrimination and hate crimes are prominent among them. They encounter prejudice in various aspects of their lives, including employment, healthcare, and education. Frequently, they grapple with societal prejudices, such as being incorrectly identified and not receiving acceptance, which can profoundly affect their emotional and psychological welfare. A study was done by The Human Rights Campaign (2021). The Human Rights Campaign tracked a record number of violent fatal incidents against transgender and gender non-conforming people, with 50 fatalities tracked. In addition to the everyday hurdles they encounter, transgender individuals also face significantly higher rates of hate crimes, physical violence, and, unfortunately, even loss of life. This underscores the urgency of prioritizing their safety and providing them with necessary protection. It is essential for society to recognize these issues and actively implement measures like legal protections, educational initiatives, and advocacy campaigns to foster a more welcoming and inclusive atmosphere. This collective effort can enable transgender individuals to lead their lives authentically, free from the perpetual threat of discrimination or violence.

According to Skuban, Orzechowski, and Steger (2022). Individuals from sexual and gender minority groups are vulnerable groups with special healthcare requirements who may face discrimination and barriers in accessing healthcare. The European Court of Human Rights judgments are systematically examined to assess their impact on limiting healthcare access for gender minority individuals and to identify and categorize discrimination against SGM individuals. Gender identity and expression receive different levels of legal recognition and protection depending on the region, requiring transgender individuals to navigate intricate legal procedures to safeguard their rights. Moreover, within the LGBTQ+ community, transgender people might experience exclusion and marginalization due to distinctions in addressing gender identity versus sexual orientation issues. Hence, it is imperative for society, encompassing healthcare systems, legal bodies, and LGBTQ+ organizations, to collaborate comprehensively in addressing these issues to ensure the well-being, dignity, and equal rights of transgender individuals. Consequently, further research is essential to grasp the distinct challenges encountered by transgender individuals in diverse geographic areas and settings, thereby guiding targeted interventions and policies aimed at achieving greater equity and inclusion.

Methodology

Research Design

A phenomenological research design was used in the study with the primary focus on understanding the lived experiences of transgender individuals. This study involved purposeful sampling of participants from diverse backgrounds, using in-depth interviews as the primary data collection method. Thematic analysis was employed to identify and categorize emergent themes, without imposing preconceived notions, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of the challenges faced by transgender individuals in the LGBTQ+ community and in broader society. The findings provide a deeper understanding of their experiences and provide informed recommendations for effectively addressing these challenges.

The phenomenological approach emphasized participants' subjective experiences, making it particularly suitable for research that sought to uncover the complexities of personal experiences and emotions related to being transgender in various societal contexts.

Participants

The researchers conducted the interview around the Mandaluyong area. The participants were given the option to choose between virtual interviews or face-to-face interviews. In-person interviews were conducted in a confidential and secure environment, and virtual interviews were conducted via Zoom. This is to set up a more flexible and to accommodate the participants' personal preferences and comfortability. These are options that make it easier for participants to be interviewed. Participants in the study were transgender individuals who were members of the LGBTQIA+ community. Creswell and Creswell (2018) suggested that 3 to 10 participants are sufficient for conducting a phenomenological study. The researchers agreed that 7 participants would participate in the study. This sample size has achieved data saturation, which is necessary to identify meta-themes or overarching themes in qualitative research.

Instrument

In this study, the researcher employed a semi-structured interviewing technique to collect data from the participants. With this approach, the interviewer created a basic framework or outline ahead of time, specifying specific topics to be covered and key questions to be asked. With this strategy, it is anticipated that comprehensive and useful data will be gathered that will help understand the experiences of transgender persons in the context of their society. The interview questions used have been thoroughly tested and specifically designed to cover the necessary topics needed to understand the unique perspectives of these individuals. Additionally, any unexpected information or insights that may emerge throughout the interview process must be considered and given due consideration.

During this research study, the participants were provided with informed consent by the researcher. This process was implemented to ensure that individuals had a comprehensive understanding of the study and were able to make an informed decision about whether they wanted to participate.

By providing informed consent, the researcher aimed to assure the participants that they were aware of every aspect of their involvement in the research. Prior to joining the study, the participants were also made aware of their right to withdraw their consent at any point if they felt that their participation could potentially harm them in any way.

Procedure

This study analyzed the challenges experienced by transgender people within and outside the LGBTQIA+ community. The researchers conducted interviews in a semi-structured format. The interview consists of open-ended questions about the respondents' individual experiences. These open-ended questions were examined and validated by experts in the field of Psychology.

Before conducting an interview, the researchers used a consent form to determine if the participants were willing to participate in the study. The researchers did an interview with seven transgender individuals. Depending on the adaptable schedules of the participants, the study was conducted via Internet and in-person interviews.

During the interview, the researchers had an ongoing recording camera to document the whole interview. The researchers explained the study's overall purpose and the ethical considerations to ensure the ability to understand the purpose of the interview for both researchers and participants.

After the interview, the researchers extended gratitude to the participants for participating in the interview. The researchers transcribed the participants' responses for coding and analysis of the data.

Ethical Considerations

Issuance of Informed Consent

The researchers issued informed consent to let the participants decide whether to participate in a face-to-face interview conducted by the researchers or a virtual interview if it conflicts with their business hours. In line with this, the participants were asked to partake in an interview with the prepared interview questions validated by the experts. The informed consent consisted of different parts: the purpose of the study, risks & benefits, confidentiality, and the rights of the participants to withdraw from participating in the interview anytime, anywhere.

Confidentiality

The researchers who are responsible for carrying out this study will be the only ones who have access to all the future gathered information and responses from this interview. The researchers gave an assurance to the participants that all the recordings that were obtained would be deleted or disposed of as soon as the final paper had been assessed and accepted to protect the participants from any potential danger.

Participants Participation and Withdrawal

The participation of the participants in this study was completely voluntary. Meaning to say, they are free to participate but they also have the right to refuse or discontinue without penalty or loss of benefits to which they may otherwise be entitled. The participants may withdraw by informing the researchers that they no longer want to participate without further questions to be asked.

Participants' Well-being

The participant's well-being was prioritized in any regard. Participants will not get their emotions or mental state disregarded; participants should feel comfortable when the interview is ongoing. It is the Researcher's ability and accessibility for the participant not to experience any discomfort or distress during the interview.

Results and Discussion

The study's emerging themes are displayed in Table 1 on the next page. Three (3) superordinate themes are formed. These are the inclusivity and setbacks in the LGBTQIA+ community, experienced challenges and barriers, and the impact of support systems in overcoming hurdles.

For each superordinate theme, there are subordinate themes that have emerged. Under the inclusivity and setbacks in the LGBTQIA+ community, there are three (3) subordinate themes: sense of belongingness, progression and growth within the rainbow community, and difficulty fitting in.

Experienced challenges and barriers are composed of six (6) subordinate themes: discrimination from academic institutions, transcultural transitions, internal social dynamics, unacceptance from the family, gender expression in mental health, and struggles with personal relationships.

In the impact of the support system on overcoming hurdles, there are four (4) subordinate themes: peer support, acceptance from beloved ones, empowerment from influential individuals, and resilience.

This research had an interview session with transgender people to understand their lived experiences that justifies the purpose of this research, which is to explore the different challenges faced by transgender people within and beyond the LGBTQ community. Interestingly, these transgender individuals have appeared to be resilient that help them to successfully navigate and overcome the challenges they've been through along with the right support structures. On the other hand, these transgender individuals had suffered

challenges, barriers, and setbacks in the LGBTQIA+ community.

Table 1.

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Inclusivity and setbacks in the LGBTQIA+ community	- Sense of belongingness - Progression and growth within the rainbow community
Experienced challenges and barriers	- Difficulty in fitting-in - Discrimination from academic institutions - Transcultural transitions - Internal social dynamics - Unacceptance from the family - Gender expression in mental health - Struggles with personal relationships
Impact of support system in overcoming hurdles	- Peer support - Acceptance from beloved ones - Empowerment from influential individualities - Resilience

The findings had an alignment with the study of JL, H. (2021) that the likelihood of experiencing violence in one's life is still four times higher for LGBT individuals than homosexual which corresponds with the setbacks, unique challenges and barriers in all aspects of life of transgender individuals. The subordinate themes for these challenges gathered these experiences from the participants:

Difficulty in Fitting In: This theme explores the complexities of competition and acceptance within the LGBT community. Even though there is mutual support from peers, they have experienced jealousy when they encountered a transgender individual in high school. Even within diverse groups, there are still challenges when it comes to maintaining solidarity. For instance, the participant felt that she was being targeted by a fellow transgender student who spread rumors about her transition and behavior. This experience highlighted the various difficulties that people encounter when trying to find support within their own community.

"In my own experience may part lang na sa LGBT kasi is not parang hindi lahat mag su-support sayo even though part sila ng LGBT, in my part kasi parang as a trans may part don sakin na inggitan ba, inggitan as a trans, as a trans sisters ko mga ganun kasi when I was in highschool parang may ka schoolmate ako na trans din sya and ayun nga dahil ewan ko kung nainggit sya sakin di naman sa pag mamayabang pero siguro yun sinisiraan nya ko sa mga, yung mga kilos ko ba lahat ng ginagawa ko sinisiraan nya ko dahil sa kung paano ako kumilos yung ganon, sa pag ta-transition ko, by that." (P3)

Discrimination from academic institutions: This theme highlights the discrimination that transgender individuals face, as schools often do not allow them to cross-dress. This practice fosters a culture of exclusion and marginalization. The policies that discriminate against transgender students have a negative impact on their academic performance and psychological health. They also contribute to the spread of inequalities and stigmas. The participant's experience shows that educational institutions must adopt policies that support and respect the diverse gender identities of their students.

"Yung ibang school hindi nila inaccept yung mga transgender na mag cross-dress." (P1)

Transcultural Transitions: The significance of cultural and historical differences in the transgender community is acknowledged by the participants. Even though they acknowledge the difficulties that deeply rooted practices and beliefs can present, they still try to bridge these gaps. The barriers that prevent transgender individuals from understanding and communicating with one another often contribute to feelings of misunderstanding and isolation.

"I think these instances has a lot of affect for us transgender because iba yung paniniwala natin so we need to do communication and kailangan nating makipag communicate sa kanila. ayun nga may instances na we're not able to communicate with them because of their culture or tradition na kinalakihan nila." (P2)

Internal Social Dynamics: This theme highlights the problematic nature of status competition within the LGBTQ community. It highlights the idea of "*nagpapataasan*," which literally means "to show off or compete for superiority." This type of behavior can foster a stratified environment that undermines the community's support and unity. The participants' emphatic rejection of this type of behavior emphasizes the crucial contribution of fostering an egalitarian and inclusive environment. This perspective emphasizes the necessity of addressing and mitigating competitive tendencies, which must ensure that the LGBTQ community maintains its egalitarian, respect, and unity.

"I have a lot of encounters inside the community, nagpapataasan and I don't like that po. To be honest sa loob ng LGBTQ community maraming nagpapataasan and I don't tolerate that po." (P3)

Family Rejection Due to Profession Based Bias: The theme talks about the rejection from family members due to desired profession. For instance, the participant says that the police officer refused to accept him because of his biases. This experience shows how certain expectations and stereotypes can affect a family's relationships. This even explores the complex relationship between personal acceptance and occupational culture. It shows how professional biases can affect a family's bond.

“Like, yung father ko kasi sya ay policeman. So, hindi niya tanggap kung ano ako.” (P4)

Gender Expression in mental health: This reveals a personal account of individuals’ experience with gender expression. The participants noted that their hair length has a significant impact on their mental health and gender identity. This talks about the mental health issues that they feel are caused by their hair. They have stated that their long hair is a big concern for them, as they think that if it wasn't long, they would look like a man. This highlights the link between gender identity and physical appearance. It also shows how people's perceptions of themselves can affect their mental health. More so, this emphasizes how important it is to support and recognize individual gender expressions to promote mental health among members of the trans community.

“Malaking hindrance siya for my mental health kasi syempre malaking bagay sa kin yung buhok ko bilang trans kasi tingin ko kapag hindi mahaba buhok ko tingin ko lalake ako.” (P5)

Struggles with Personal Relationships: This explores the difficulties that LGBTQ+ individuals encounter in their personal relationships. Although their relatives typically acknowledge their sexual preference, they encounter difficulties in expressing their identity due to their conditional acceptance. The approval given to a family member is contingent on strict conditions, such as prohibiting the appearance of being gay, and wearing feminine clothing. This partial acceptance can create an environment where the individual's true self is not fully expressed, which can lead to conflict within the family. This shows how complex acceptance can be for LGBTQ+ individuals when surface-level tolerance is not enough to make them feel supported and understood.

“One of my family members ay hindi ako tanggap yung reason dun is okay naman sa kanya na maging gay ako pero ang catch dun bawal ko gawin yung ginagawa ng gay tulad ng pananamit ng babae, pagpapahaba (ng buhok) basta okay lang sa family member ko na yon.” (P6)

With this, the results indicated that most of the transgender individuals are still experiencing negative treatment within and beyond the LGBTQ community. Although some of them are being accepted by the community, which proposes progress for transgender individuals.

Conclusions

The subordinate themes explore into discrimination faced by transgender individuals, social dynamics, acceptance, mental health, etc. These challenges emphasize the findings of Mozumder (2022) regarding the nature of discrimination can extend beyond various case of abuse, which leads to deteriorating mental health. Overall, themes on the challenges faced by transgender individuals leading from institutions, transitions, social dynamics, unacceptance, and gender expression. These challenges contribute to a deeper understanding of the obstacles faced by the participants within the LGBTQIA community.

Unfold from the study’s literature review, the study’s finding call for a societal change and increase for awareness to further combat the discrimination and promote inclusivity within the LGBTQIA+ community, this emphasizes the role of societal norms and values, suggesting that change may take time and requires various approach. (Pearce 2020; Turban 2022)

The themes expressed within the LGBTQIA+ community, with participants conflicted with the balance of inclusivity and setbacks. Despite the challenges faced in their normal lives, the belongingness among its community shares a common journey of progression and growth, with the LGTBQIA+ integrating unity, diversity, and inclusivity remains intact. However, there will always be imperfections even within the community, having difficulties of fitting into their societal norms, and having expectations, these have been highlighted by the participants on their struggles within the LGBTQIA+ individuals. These certain setbacks can reflect a nuanced experience that brings out resilience within or outside the community.

Regardless, further research will always be recommended. This could involve deeper exploration of the study’s themes, relatively exploring the perspectives and experiences of future individuals who have successfully overcome societal norms and expectations within the LGBTQIA+ community, this could provide valuable insights that can be potential for growth and empowerment. This suggested approach will not only acknowledge the existing challenges but also bring light on interventions, and practices that can contribute to fostering more supporting and inclusive community or the environment itself for LGBTQIA+ individuals.

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